

INTENSIFICATION IN LANGUAGE AND SPEECH

Abdullaeva S.M.

Teacher of Uzbek State World Languages university

Tashkent, Uzbekistan

sevara_a_98@mail.ru

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Following P.A. Lekant, intensification in language and speech can be understood as a number of functional-semantic operations, including emphasis (accentuation), strengthening, completeness, gradation (usually its high degree), generalization and evaluation [Lekant 2011: 58]. Intensification is associated with the expression of emotions of a native speaker, for whom it is important to strengthen the semantics of his words in a given situation. This is why U. Labov believes that the means of linguistic intensification underlie social and emotional expression in the speaker's speech [Labov 1984: 43].

A. Vezhbetskaya points out that hyperbolization, as a means of "expressing any assessments - both positive and negative, is a striking feature of modern language that uses intensifying means [Vezhbetskaya 1996: 84]. Indeed, in the colloquial speech of native speakers, in advertising, on the Internet and other sources one can often hear/see such phrases as supernutritious bar, grandiose scandal, etc.

It is worth noting that the functional-semantic category of intensity has the property of universality: the means of its expression cover linguistic units of different levels - verbs, adjectives, adverbs, pronouns, nouns, phraseological units, complete texts, etc. [Bezrukova 2004]. The intensifier quite as a source of new units

This paper analyzes the adverb quite in its various implementations in speech (in particular, as part of a construction and a hashtag). This word is a source of expression in the intensifiers under consideration.

The analyzed adverb quite is an adverb of measure and degree, indicating a different degree of manifestation of some feature. Adverbs of measure and degree are defined as lexical and phraseological units that perform the "function of indicating the degree of magnitude or the evaluation of the feature of the subject of speech" [Khovalkina 1996: 80]. This group of adverbs was noted in the works of V.V. Vinogradov, N.N. Prokopovich, I.P. Slesareva, A.N. Baranov, V.A. Plungyan, E.V. Rakhilina, E. Krzhizhkova, A.A. Khovalkina, and others.

S.A. Grigorieva in the "New Explanatory Dictionary of Synonyms of the Russian Language" defines it as an adverb indicating "higher intensity of the

final state” [Grigoryeva 2003: 1082]. The definition of the adverb 'completely' is also given in the 'Guide to Discourse Words of the Russian Language', where its meaning of 'completion/culmination of the process', named by the word interacting with the given adverb, is noted [Baranov, Plungyan, Rakhilina 1993: 148]. And finally, the academic dictionary gives the following definition: 'completely, completely' [MAS 1988: 177].

From these definitions, we can conclude that the adverb *soveye* reflects gradation, i.e. indicates a high degree of the value of a feature. This, as one might assume, was the reason for the formation of the construction from the word *soveye*, to which the adverb “gave” the same semantics.

Researchers analyzing the construction from the word *soveye*, note that “the phraseological expression in question” came from a “free combination from the word”, which is usually used as a reference to the etymology of the word. However, in the new meaning, “from the word *soveye* refers to the axis of syntagmatics, that is, *soveye* <...> is syntagmatically connected with the words of this or the previous sentence” [Voznesenskaya, Severskaya 2019: 477].

S.S. Belousov in his 2016 work “From the word *soveye* as a grammatical construction” [Belousov 2016] presented the first case of using this construction. He managed to find an example of the use of the construction on one of the forums, where a man from the city of Volgodonsk wrote the following in 2005: The only major drawback is that it is not waterproof, not at all [CONFERENCE on AIRSOFTGUN.RU: elec. rksurs].

Since 2005, the construction has been developing and functioning in the texts of blogs in various social networks. It is important to note that there is no single type of this construction. The following spelling options were identified during the study:

1) using a comma separating the construction or hashtag from the main sentence

And I don't know it at all, not at all;

Perhaps #detective, #fantasy, drama or a whirlwind romance are not interesting, #fromwordsatall;

2) using a period, resulting in a parceled construction

Now all targeted/contextual advertising on the network will have to be marked. From the word absolutely;

Everything works differently.

3) using ellipsis, intonationally highlighting the construction or hashtag:

And household chores NEVER end ... from the word absolutely

With you by my side it's not scary at all...

As further evidence of the thesis about the many spelling options for the construction in question, let's turn to sentences written in 2013, 2017 and 2019, respectively:

The Logitech Kinetik Backpack hard laptop backpack has disappeared from sale, from the word absolutely;

We decided to look at luxury real estate for the sake of contrast and beautiful shots and suddenly learned from a local expert that it does not exist - from the word "absolutely";

I'll leave this life - no one will need it from the word "abso-lute".

Thus, the semantics of the original adverb quite "subordinates" both the construction created on its basis and the hashtag. The proposed "intensification scale": quite - from the word "quite" - demonstrates graphic and related semantic changes that contribute to the strengthening of the intensification of a particular linguistic expression.

It is especially important to note that a feature of modern Russian speech is the use of intensifying means. Due to this, the construction from the word quite gained popularity, and subsequently the hashtag.

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